

UNDERSTANDING UZBEK TEXTS IN ENGLISH

Rasuljonova Saida

School teacher No. 191 of Tashkent City

Abstract: In this article includes it should be said that communication between people is carried out through the means of communication texts (and this is recognized by the creators of text linguistics, in general, by the majority of text researchers), limiting the text only to the written form contradicts the existing rules of text theory. After all, it is impossible to imagine that any communication between people takes place only and only in written form.

Keywords: informative text, order-desire meaningful text, emotional expression meaningful text, theme- rheumatic attitude.

Even though cohesion is not maintained in this example, the text producer still succeeds in achieving the goal of finding out if the text receiver wanted a piggyback. Acceptability concerns the text receiver's attitude that the text should constitute useful or relevant details or information worth accepting. Text type, the desirability of goals, and the political and sociocultural setting, as well as cohesion and coherence, are important in influencing the acceptability of a text.

Text producers often speculate on the receiver's attitude of acceptability and present texts that maximize the probability that the receivers will respond as desired by the producers. For example, texts that are open to a wide range of interpretations, such as "Call us before you dig. You may not be able to afterward" require more inferences about the related consequences. This is more effective than an explicit version of the message that informs receivers of the full consequences of digging without calling because receivers are left with great uncertainty as to the consequences that could result; this plays to people's risk aversion.

Informativity concerns the extent to which the contents of a text are already known or expected as compared to unknown or unexpected. No matter how expected or predictable content may be, a text will always be informative at least to a certain degree due to unforeseen variability. The processing of highly informative text demands greater cognitive ability but at the same time is more interesting. The level

of informativity should not exceed a point such that the text becomes too complicated and communication is endangered. Conversely, the level of informativity should also not be so low that it results in boredom and the rejection of the text.

Situationality concerns the factors which make a text relevant to a situation of occurrence. The situation in which a text is exchanged influences the comprehension of the text. There may be different interpretations of the road sign

SLOW

CARS

HELD UP

However, the most likely interpretation of the text is obvious because the situation in which the text is presented provides the context which influences how text receivers interpret the text. The group of receivers (motorists) who are required to provide a particular action will find it more reasonable to assume that "slow" requires them to slow down rather than referring to the speed of the cars that are ahead. Pedestrians can tell easily that the text is not directed towards them because varying their speeds is inconsequential and irrelevant to the situation. In this way, the situation decides the sense and use of the text.

Situationality can affect the means of cohesion; the less cohesive text may be more appropriate than more cohesive text depending on the situation. If the road sign was "Motorists should reduce their speed and proceed slowly because the vehicles ahead are held up by road works, therefore proceeding at too high a speed may result in an accident', every possible doubt of intended receivers and intention would be removed. However, motorists only have a very short amount of time and attention to focus on and react to road signs. Therefore, in such a case, the economical use of text is much more effective and appropriate than a fully cohesive text.

Intertextuality concerns the factors which make the utilization of one text dependent upon knowledge of one or more previously encountered texts. If a text receiver does not have prior knowledge of a relevant text, communication may break down because the understanding of the current text is obscured. For texts such as parodies, rebuttals, forums, and classes in school, the text producer has to refer to prior texts while the text receivers have to have knowledge of the prior texts for communication to be efficient or even occur. In other text types such as puns, for

example, "Time flies like an arrow; fruit flies like a banana', there is no need to refer to any other text.

Research shows that the text is divided into two according to the size and content sign:

1. Types of text according to size.
2. Text types according to the content of the expression.

Text types by size: A text is a medium of large-scale communication, a speech activity, rather than a sentence product, written speech formed on the basis of certain laws it looks like. We divide the text according to the size symbol: Minimum text and max text. Descriptive texts Such as a person, place, animal, etc. unknown to the text listener a creature or thing belonging to the plant kingdom and was created in order to describe the incident in detail will be. The appearance of a monologic speech in a visual text is leadership does. The patronymic image is the most characteristic feature of such a text is considered That is, the first, primary object of the depicted object feature is mentioned. Then the properties related to it and its parts are discussed:

For example: Aslida esa yakan –qamishzorda o‘suvcchi o‘simlik. Yakanni o‘rib olib, quritib uzum osadilar yoki savat qalpoq to‘qiydilar. Ma‘lumki, qamish uzun, yakan esa, aksincha, pastak o‘simlik

Explanatory texts: To emphasize the persuasiveness of the thought expressed in such a text various arguments and explanations are presented. To justify, to prove, to justify oneself attempt or defense to make various excuses is one of the unique aspects of the meaningful text type. With thought, it is important that there is a logical connection between the presented evidence is counted. Units such as chunki, zero, lekin, aslida, shuning uchun, to‘g‘risini (ochig‘ini, rostini) aytganda, eshitishimga qaraganda, bilishimcha, taxminimcha in a text we will see if it is used.

Didactic texts to someone admonish, and educate him through various life events or on the basis of the desire to teach to draw conclusions from what was said structured text is called didactic text. A proverb, saying, aphorism used in the text with a specific purpose, various life events, narratives, and parables are called didactema. Didactems are incorporated into the text in different ways. The author brings such didactems directly into the text and tells what genre it belongs to. Texts with message content: Created for the purpose of reporting an event or Linked text is the content of the message. Artistic the text is informative in its own way. In

everyday life is fundamentally different from a simple message. The message in the literary text is aesthetic it is distinguished by its goal orientation. Such a message will be related to the whole work. The story, image, explanation, and didactic.

The command comes in the form of meaningful text types. Texts with a command-desire content Command - where the tone of desire or advice leads, made up of imperative sentences, doing something or different command to the type of text that expresses prohibitions - desire is meaningfully called text. Texts with emotional expression are the inner experiences of a person, negative or positive to reality the text expressing the attitude with its own pathos is an emotional expression is called meaningful text.

CONCLUSION

The concept of text in Uzbek and English refers to a coherent piece of written or spoken language that conveys meaning, consisting of smaller linguistic units such as words, phrases, and sentences. The main purpose of the text is to convey a message or idea to the reader or listener.

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